

НОВО ДОБА:

ЖИВОТ МАЈКЕ И БЕБЕ У НЕОЛИТУ БАЛКАНА

NEW AGE:

the lives of mothers and
babies in the Balkan
Neolithic

BIRTH

Births, mothers and babies:
Prehistoric fertility in the Balkans
between 10000-5000 BC

European Research Council
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